

Euphorbia sekukuniensis Sekhukhune candelabra tree

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 2 m

Distribution:

Endemic to South Africa, only known to the Limpopo and Mpumalanga Provinces. It occurs in the Lydenburg District, Sekhukhuneland, the Steelpoort River Valley and to the Olifants River.

Importance:

The Sekhukhune candelabra tree is a popular ornamental plant. It has a restricted distribution in isolated populations on shallow norite soils and is threatened by mining activities. In southern Africa, the Euphorbiaceae family faces increasing pressure from illegal collection and habitat loss. Over 30 species are listed as threatened and many others are data-deficient or unevaluated, highlighting the need for urgent conservation action.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 84.83 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 17.59 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 2.58 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.8% [Single: 78.4%, Duplicated: 21.4%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 24 098.04 kilobases

Contig number: 658

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